

FORECAST OF THE FUTURE POTENTIAL OF THE ANTIPSYCHOTIC DRUG MARKET IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Relevance of the Topic: Strategic planning in the pharmaceutical market is key to effective medication supply. This requires the analysis of a large volume of market information, where forecasting plays an important role. It helps companies to develop assortment and pricing policies as well as promotion strategies. This is especially important for providing patients with depression—a socially significant disease that requires stable access to modern and safe antipsychotic medications. The relevance of the topic is connected with growing competition and market instability. Reliable forecasting models can enhance the efficiency of business processes and ensure uninterrupted drug supply. This approach will help companies optimize production and marketing.

Objective of the Study: The aim of the study is to develop a forecast of the future market volumes of antidepressants until 2025. This approach enables pharmaceutical companies to more accurately optimize procurement and production capacities, minimizing the risk of shortages during peak seasons and avoiding unnecessary costs by planning supplies during low-demand periods.

Materials and Methods: In the forecasting process, the methodology [2] was used, which was subsequently adapted to the specific characteristics of the studied market.

Results Obtained: The analysis of sales forecast graphs revealed the following features: the criterion for selecting data for all items was not the stability of monthly supply throughout the research period [1,3]. Since the forecasting methodology requires the continuity of monthly demand data [2].

As a result of the calculations, it was found that the cumulative base forecast of the antipsychotic drug market for 2025 amounted to 1,314,662 packages, the pessimistic forecast to 231,782 packages, and the optimistic forecast to 2,861,105 packages respectively (Figure 1). The forecasting model considers both seasonal fluctuations and the overall growth trend. This suggests that the cyclical nature of sales will continue in the future, with peaks in the

spring and autumn periods, and each subsequent peak is likely to be slightly higher than the previous one. The difference between optimistic and pessimistic forecasts increases over time, indicating growing uncertainty in the long term.

It was found that the total volume of production and imports (hereinafter referred to as market availability) of antipsychotics shows growth over the studied period, as indicated by the trend line (linear). A conditional trend of seasonal availability of antipsychotics at certain times of the year was also identified. Overall, the antipsychotic drug market demonstrates stable growth, indicating increased demand for this category of drugs.

Based on the research results and forecast calculations illustrated in the diagram, the highest demand for antipsychotic drugs sharply increases in November and May—during the spring-autumn seasons. During the studied years (2018–2023), the lowest demand was observed in the summer months, with the highest demand being 268,127 in May 2023, while the lowest was 6,580 in July 2023. Based on this conclusion, purchases in the following years can be planned according to these requirements—either increasing procurement in November and May or reducing it in June and January.

Figure 1. Dynamics of optimistic, pessimistic, and linear forecasts for all antipsychotics for the year 2025

These invaluable conclusions are of great importance, as they allow us to be prepared in advance for a sudden increase in demand, preventing interruptions in antipsychotic production in our market. At the same time, we can avoid excessive costs by making fewer purchases during the summer and autumn months. This data will help us make informed purchasing decisions based on forecasts for future years.

Unusual forecast peaks for 2024 and 2025 were identified, allowing us to observe the actual results for those years. In 2024, the total number of

antipsychotics is expected to be 1,254,903 packages, with the pessimistic forecast at 34,252 packages—this figure corresponds to the month of June—and the optimistic forecast at 199,526 packages (Figure 2.18). In 2025, the total quantity may reach 1,361,644 packages, with the most pessimistic forecast at 38,570 (for June) and the most optimistic at 214,662 (for November). From these forecast results, we see that the quantity of antipsychotics is increasing year by year, and even the minimum figures are growing by at least 4,000 packages. The highest figures in 2024 and 2025 correspond to November, followed by April and May. During these seasons, it is important to purchase and import more antipsychotics in accordance with demand based on the above criteria to avoid shortages. The lowest indicators appear in June, followed by October and January. On the other hand, if attention is given to the quantity of antipsychotics in these months, and imports are made in smaller quantities based on the numbers mentioned above, this will eliminate unnecessary costs and problems.

The study of the dynamics of antipsychotic sales in the market and the development of forecasting models made it possible to identify key trends and factors affecting demand in this segment of the pharmaceutical market.

Conclusion: The main conclusions of the study can be summarized as follows: Most medications show pronounced seasonality in antipsychotic sales, especially noticeable in November. This may be due to seasonal fluctuations in population stress and anxiety levels, with weather variability in November, April, and May possibly being a root cause. Trend analysis was conducted, and a seasonality factor in the consumption of the studied group of drugs as a whole was identified. A relatively dynamic growth in the consumption of antipsychotics over the period 2024–2025 was found. The average monthly availability of antipsychotics on the market increased from 1,083,072 (2023) to 1,361,644–1,556,397 (2025). An adapted forecasting methodology for the market based on trend indicators was tested. The methodology was applied to forecast aggregate market indicators.

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